

PEDAGOGICAL STRATEGIES IN PAKISTANI ISLAMIC ANIMATED CARTOONS: A QUALITATIVE CONTENT ANALYSIS OF KANEEZ FATIMA AND GHULAM RASOOL ANIMATED SERIES

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Abstract

Due to the significant rise in animation all over the world, it bridges the gap between traditional and modern ages by communicating values, beliefs and culture thorough visual, lingual and narrative structures. This study examines the children's animated cartoons Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool using Corpus-Assisted Discourse Studies of selected 40 episodes, 20 from each series. The research analyzes how children's animated cartoons embody and transmit moral, religious, and behavioral values through various pedagogical strategies. For this purpose, a specialized corpus was developed from the transcribed dialogues of the selected episodes and analyzed through Sketch Engine's tools keyword analysis and concordance analysis to identify frequently occurring lexical items related to objectives as remember, should, dear children, reward, forgive, apologize, help, Allah, Salah, and other devotional expressions. The results emphasize the application of several methods for teaching, such as modeling, repetition, audience engagement strategies, reinforcement strategies, and direct instruction through commands. The results show that reinforcement techniques operate through corrective mechanisms based on allusions to the Quran and Hadith and positive repercussions (divine reward, praise, forgiveness). Direct audience address, such as "Dear children," serves as an engagement technique that improves learner positioning and attention. In line with Bandura's social learning theory, demonstrative modeling of rituals like Salah, fasting, supplication, and common manners closes the knowledge-practice gap. Repeating important Islamic words acts as scaffolding, strengthening memory and normalizing Islamic customs in children's imagined worlds. The study concludes that these cartoons function as structured pedagogical tools that integrate linguistic reinforcement, symbolic modeling, and interactive discourse to cultivate Islamic moral identity and behavioral self-regulation among young viewers.

Introduction

In the late 20th century with digital advancements and massive use of media technology, a new form of preaching has emerged (Mueleman, 2011). The propagation of information has changed all over the world in today's world of digital communication. The basis of social change is technological progress (Lewis, 2014). In the dire need to spread the religious perspectives, belief and ideology, and educate their believers to correct their religious practices, various religions in the world are heavily relying on the digital media (Zaid et al., 2022). According to Ishak and Solihin (2012), for preaching Islam and Islamic teachings, digital media has been highly stressed as the useful resource. Pakistan has also witnessed the growth of religious preaching through the use of digital media among the young audience due their high accessibility for the public. Youth is using this digital media to have access to correct their religious practices, gain guidance and religious information (Yahya et al., 2021). According to mediatization theory, religion is becoming increasingly interconnected with interactive and audiovisual media, which is changing the way that beliefs are expressed and internalized (Wei 2024).

Animation is also used as an instructional technique to teach Islamic fundamental principles to younger generations effortlessly. Digital platforms like YouTube have become an effective medium for debating and preaching religious ideologies among various streams recently (Al Mushaiqri & Sulistio, 2024).

Due to the rise of technology and massive use of media by people of ages including children, the content is very crucial as they gain much knowledge while observing. Religious media is an absolute need for children to keep them connected to their 'Deen' these days. Among these, Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool animated cartoons are very popular and these series are referred to due to their high visual and narrative appeal. The episodes include moral lessons, Islamic beliefs, teaching about important religious events, Quranic Ayyah's and special episodes about Quran in Ramadan. Thus, these series hold a significant place among many others in teaching digital religion. The characters in Ghulam Rasool and Kaneez Fatima do more than just providing entertainment; they serve as role models for moral behaviour, gender performance, and religious commitment, all of which, kids may internalize as a part of who they are. Faqihuddin (2024) states the importance of digital technology to enhance the memorization of Quran utilizing multimodal method which combines various components

including visual, auditory and kinesthetic. Animated films particularly with its techniques to show “reality” and expression like story telling provide a contested site for the formation of identity (Yoshida, 2008).

Research Objectives

The study is based on the following objectives:

- To determine the pedagogical approaches used in selected episodes Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool series
- To explore the ways moral and religious values are constructed and taught through characters, dialogue, and narrative structure in the selected episodes

Literature Review

The significance of visual communication in instructional practices is highlighted by various scholars (Arnheim, 1969; Barlex & Carré, 1985; Fisher, 1990). Specifically, Bliss, Ogborn, and Whitelock (1989) highlighted the motivational impact of cartoon-style materials in their research. As animation progressed, cartoon characters came to life and became a standard in filmmaking world. Animation plays significantly shape children’s social and moral understanding. A study of Pakistani animated movie 3 Bahadur by Zulfiqar and Ahmed (2025), examines the animated film ichnographically through Panofsky’s three step framework. It shows that characters represent social responsibility, moral binaries, patriotism, social responsibility, and women empowerment showcasing traits of Pakistani culture exhibited through animation.

Studies about Islamic values are abundant on featuring digital content. According to studies, in digital content various manifestations of Islamic piety are frequently depicted. In order to survive with the global society, some varieties focus universal principles like family bonds, moral behavior, and compassion which catch the attention of wide range of audiences. Conversely, other kinds openly challenge modern cultural standards or promote exclusive interpretations of religious practices that run counter to global culture (Aidulsyah, 2023; Heryanto, 2014; Juliansyahzen, 2023).

To improve comprehensive memorisation of the Qur'an, a multimodal method utilising digital technology that combines kinaesthetic, visual, and auditory components has been suggested (Faqihuddin, 2024). Dewi and Negara (2021) further illustrates the role of technology in learning as it aids mentors to convey the material, instruction and knowledge to

students extensively. The use of technology in learning extensively helps teachers to convey information to students.

A study by Warini et al., (2024) explores the process of learning through the use of animation media based on videos. They proved that learning in a Junior High School using animated videos is feasible and as compared to traditional teaching methods.

Media tools have gained significant prominence for teaching young audiences. Yousaf et al., (2022) conducted a qualitative study to explore the effectiveness of teaching religious values to school-going children in Sheikhpura city. They took observations and interviews with teachers and parents and shown cartoons to children based on religious instructions. The findings confirm that teaching early religious education, cartoons help children to develop understanding and adopting religious values and children try to follow them.

Tafonao also highlights the role of media in teaching and learning process. He explains that learning media is inseparable part of education in the instructional process. Students' attention, interest and perception is stimulated by the learning media as it passes instructions from the sender to recipient (Tafonao, 2018).

Warini et al., (2024) argues that Islamic religious education effectively impact person's life despite the changes are minor. He elaborates that by making intriguing and interesting animated videos, we can develop interest in Islamic religious education. While teaching the generation of millennials and strawberry, this is tough because of the flow of technology, their morals are lessened. Therefore, teaching through learning media is important for younger generations. As it makes the atmosphere lively and enjoyable for students particularly using computer media without sacrificing the important lesson we need to taught to them (Suryana & Hijriani, 2022).

In the recent industrial revolution and technological advancements era, to make the teaching and learning effective and enjoyable, technology should improve teaching materials and media to enhance and support learning (Lia et al., 2023). This mode of learning is justified and confirmed further by studies, as Mushtaq and Fatima (2024) study the effects of cartoons on learning attitude. For this they take a sample of 205 kids from urban preschools and primary schools, ages 3 to 7. The findings of the study confirm that to improve children learning outcomes, instructional cartoons are capable to improve their attitudes and experiences. Further studies also highlight the importance of moral instruction via narratives.

Abdullah (2023) argues that pre-school children learn Islamic moral values through imitation and cartoons model behavior shapes the moral development and understanding in children along with families' explanations of good and bad values.

Methodology

This study uses a Corpus-Assisted Qualitative Discourse Analysis approach to examine the pedagogical approaches used in the cartoons as verbal evidence not only visual. For the study, data comprised over 40 episodes from both series of Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool were taken. Transcripts of all episodes were compiled in UTF-8 encoded plain-text (.txt) file. The data for both series were taken from three YouTube channels named as Kids Land, Madani Channal English and DawateIslami English. The corpus comprised over 29,461 words combined. And individually, sub corpora of Kaneez Fatima discourse comprised over 16,037 words and of Ghulam Rasool approximately 13,424 words. First the corpus analysis of specialized corpus of Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam is conducted through Sketch Engine using several analysis tools such as keywords, wordlist, word sketch, and concordance. Following this corpus analysis, corpus-driven thematic interpretation was conducted which involves grouping recurrent and similar lexical items into broader conceptual categories and themes. For Corpus analysis, Sketch Engine was used. The file of compiled corpus Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool was compared with British National Corpus (BNC) available in sketch engine to get keywords and concordance analysis.

Analysis and Discussion

Pedagogical Approaches in Teaching Islamic Concepts

The corpus analysis of Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool discourse highlights various teaching strategies to instruct and guide children social, religious and moral values within Islamic educational context. Using Gee's analytical tools of inquiry especially his situated meaning tool, social languages tool, and Bandura's Social learning theory including his observational learning, reinforcement, and modeling, these strategies are reflected and explained. Together, these frameworks show how language in the series functions not only to convey information but to shape behavior, identity, and moral understanding among children. The different pedagogical strategies are discussed below.

Direct Instruction through Commands

The phrases that convey orders or requests to the viewer are called command impressions. These include expressions such as “you must”, “you should”, and imperative verb remember. The first keyword analysis to identify command expressions include the word ‘should’. The occurrence of this search word model verb Should is 221. In both corpora, these expressions appeared frequently and align with Gee’s tools of inquiry that language acts as performative functions, it helps in build identities, structure relationships and guide practices (Gee,2011). In corpus, these expressions perform the function of teaching, instructing children to adopt good behavior and practices. For example statements like; “And Raiqa the most important thing is that you should have trust upon Allah Almighty and have reliance in Him.”, “Then Raiqa you should also recite it.”, “And also Raiqa whenever you drink water you should do so by reciting Bismillah”., “You should not physically harm the animal of sacrifice like this.”, and the expressions “we should” functions as soft command; “We should go and get ready to offer Zuhr Salah.”, “We should first offer Salah, and all other things can also be done later.”, “We should always be grateful to Allah for what He blessed us with.”, “We shouldn't waste time whilst fasting rather we should perform pious deeds.” The expression of “we should” occurred in the context of moral teachings as not listening other people communications, not harm animals, not hurt feelings of others etc. and communicating necessary obligations and religious teachings like performing Salah, following Hazrat Bibi Fatima, making a lot of duas from Allah, seeking forgiveness, in terms of teaching manners of eating, drinking and living.

The frequency of imperative remember is 25 and it appears in the context of religious instruction, moral reinforcement and teaching important moral lessons to children. The lead instructors; Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool use this keyword as a pedagogical soft imperative as a gentle reminder with emotional care. The occurrence of imperative expressions further communicates the necessity Islamic expectations to be adopted. Statements such as;

“remember that backbiting burns the pious deeds of a person.”, “And remember Allah Almighty because Allah Almighty says in the Holy Quran...”.

From the Bandura's perspective, verbal instructions and commands are the form of modeling, through authoritative guidance, children learn appropriate behaviors from symbolic 101 models. This mode of learning is justified and confirmed further by studies, as Mushtaq & Fatima (2024) study the effects of cartoons on learning attitude. For this they take a sample of 205 kids from urban preschools and primary schools, ages 3 to 7. The findings of the study confirm that to improve children learning outcomes, instructional cartoons are capable to improve their attitudes and experiences. Thus, direct instruction entails the Islamic code and conducts and shapes children's understanding.

Reinforcement Strategies: Motivation Through Rewards, Consequences, and Ethical Reasoning

The occurrence of keywords such as reward, forgive, apologize and help construct moral framework of cause-and-effect and linguistic presence of reinforcement. In occurrences these expressions teach and guide other to adopt correct moral behavior. The word reward occurs in the corpus 11 times and is used in the discourse as a praise for those who follow the right path as in Islamic pedagogy, associated with virtue and consequences of morally and behaviorally good actions. such as; “Raiqa giving water to others is a great act of reward.”, “Please forgive me sis I will not do this again in future”, “Allah, Allah! Please forgive me”, “You have to apologise to her”, “And helping out any fellow Muslim is such a tremendous act.”

Details	Left context	KWIC	Right context
1	doc#0 any water for you.	Raiqa giving water to others is a great act of reward	The final Messenger of Sallelahu Elehi WaAlehi Wasslam ha:
2	doc#0 uch to plant trees to the extent that you can also plant trees to convey	reward	to other people.
3	doc#0 / reward to other people.	We should also plant trees to convey reward	to the Holy Prophet Sallelahu Elehi WaAlehi Wasslam, all the compan
4	doc#0 sation and all your activities and reply to the Azan and earn abundant	reward	Okay you go and get ready for Salah and I'll just clean the kitchen thei
5	doc#0 ictivities and conversation and reply to the Azan and earn abundant of	reward	It's time to offer Salah now.
6	doc#0 g show off.	Allah will say on the Day of Judgement when He is rewarding	the people for their actions: Go to those for whom you did riya for in th
7	doc#0 to those for whom you did riya for in the world then see if you find the	reward	with them."
8	doc#0 ersation and all the activities and reply to the azan and earn abundant	reward	Do you and Zainab know method of Salah?
9	doc#0 ow many different tasty dishes they have prepared.	May Allah reward	brother Numan and his family for this.
10	doc#0 -being.	Okay	Brother Ghulam Rasool do we also get a reward
11	doc#0 ssalamu Alaikum Warahmatullahi WaBarakatu and earn abundant of	reward	Brother Faizan, please turn off the camera for a little while.

From the Gee's situated meaning tool; the context specific meanings these words take on reinforce Islamic ethics. For example, the word reward meaning divine reward as the consequences of worldly actions not only material benefits. The frequency of 'apologize' is 16 and 'forgive' is 13. The occurrences of words in context reinforce positive behavior through the depiction of reward, apology, forgiveness and helping others in need. As children observes these symbolic models and motivated by the outcomes. Positive consequences of good actions as helping, praying, apologizing, greetings, honesty, kindness and respect are praised by words 'MashaAllah' and 'JazakAllah' in the series, and 'Astagfirullah' is used for negative behaviors by characters such as lying, hurting, humiliating, disobeying, breaking promises, harming are corrected in the series through Quran and Hadith. These behaviors become models for the viewers.

The word 'help' in the corpus occurred 30 times but in different contexts, in some instances used as direct moral instruction in statements like "Helping out others is a great deed" stated by Dad of Kaneez Fatima, "And helping out any fellow Muslim is such a tremendous act". Allah Almighty states in the Quran: Chapter 27, "wayu'sirona ala anfusahum wa lau kana bihim khasasa" "And they give preference over themselves even if they themselves are in need", the reason of helping someone as Allah please with one who helps others, poor people and give Sadaqah. This word is also used in terms of narrative requests for instance, excuse me! can you help me please? and in family contexts for girls as Kaneez Fatima asks Raiqa that "we can help out Mom in household activities, engage ourselves in art and craft".The characters repent and apologize over their actions. For this Anas ibn Malik reported: The Prophet, peace and blessings be upon him, said, "All of the children of Adam are sinners, and the best sinners are those who repent." (Sunan al-Tirmidhi 2499).

In a nutshell, the narratives of Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool demonstrate positive consequences are virtuous actions and negative consequences are misbehavior and lead instructors immediately correct those behaviors that align with Islamic ethical frameworks. Performing good deeds is associated with reward from Allah and apologizing and forgiving others models interpersonal ethics that helps in build good relationships as Bandura argues language helps to build identities and relationships. Characteristics such as ‘calmness’ and ‘politeness’ are also appeared as keywords embodies the character with polite behavior and calmness in doing every word including Salah as Salah is with calmness. These pedagogical approaches engage children in moral reasoning, allowing them to understand the social and spiritual outcomes of actions they perform and do self-evaluation. Cartoons have a positive effect on teaching religious values and education to children. It is observed by the study through content analysis of 30 episodes of Ramazan Tayfa film that cartoons can transfer religious education to children and can play an active role in creating and managing awareness of religious teachings (Yolcu & Ciftci, 2023). Further studies also highlight the importance of moral instruction via narratives. Abdullah (2023) argues that pre-school children learn Islamic moral values through imitation and cartoons model behavior shapes the moral development and understanding in children along with families’ explanations of good and bad values.

Audience Engagement Strategies

In the discourse, expression such as ‘Dear children’ is used to directly address with audience children who are watching and consumers of the content that establish a conversational and affinity-building discourse strategy that enhances audience engagement through inviting and interactive tone. This phrase is used 18 times across both series. For instance; “Dear children, you should also follow these good manners, and join me in repeating the dua of after eating food.”, “Dear children whenever you feel scared then recite Auzubillah minashaitan nirajeem,

then Ayatul Kursi and the last two surahs of Holy Quran; Surahatul Falaq and Surahatun Nas.”, “Dear children we should never lose hope in the mercy of Allah Almighty which is never ending and never gives up the hard work.”

Instead of direct instructional methods, this expression in occurrences serves as interactive discursive strategy by directly positioning audience as the learner and listeners. Bandura's social learning theory (1977) argues that children imitate the model behaviors through modeling process and four conditions are needed in this. The first condition to model a behavior is attention. Children imitate the modeled behavior when their attention is effectively captured. In the series of Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool, different elements and strategies are used to capture the children's attention such as playing games, use of gestures and colors, and more important by directly calling the audience. This increases selective attention, understanding and more emotionally relatable content to children. The direct address of characters, appear more familiar and trustworthy connection with audience make them imitate the symbolic models. Previous study in Pakistan context highlights significance of religious cartoons in understanding and attempting to follow these instructions. Cartoons effectively teach and enhance learning ability by using audio-visual effects and a source of religious instruction due to being highly scripted (Yousaf et al., 2022).

Modeling Through Demonstration

Another prominent strategy used in the series is demonstrative modeling where characters perform Islamic rituals and shapes model Islamic behavior such as greetings verbally and with shaking hands as Ghulam Rasool and other male characters do in the series, helping others such as giving iftar party to poor in Ramadan, helping neighbors, inquiring the ill, manners of eating and drinking and entering someone else's house, use of devotional expressions in contexts and different occasions as SubhanAllah (20), Alhamdulillah (27), Allah hu Akbar (31), JazakAllah (37), MashaAllah (34), InshaAllah (26), and Astagfirullah (9), reciting Bismillah (16) before doing anything involving eating, and teaching method of Salah for women by Ghulam

Rasool as step-by-step guide in occurrences “*Let me teach you both the method of Islamic sister Salah. so first of all, you have to say Allah hu Akbar and raise your hands up to the shoulders under your scarf or the shawl. Place the palm of the left hand on your chest then on the back of your left hand place the palm of the right hand in this way...*” and teaches through a 3D demonstrative model of a women and performing religious practices as keeping fast, reciting Quran, reciting duas on different occasions like entering house, entering washroom, dua for sleeping and travelling etc. All these occurs linguistically and visually explicit way. The discourse involves all the evidences of these actions. Though this is not just symbolic modeling or abstract, but viewers can actually see physical actions, watch the characters correct or guide others, hear the narration and actions alongside through the process of demonstrations. This strategy is important as it bridges the gap between knowledge and practice. Modeling, self-efficacy and mentoring are the principles 104 of Bandura’s theory that can be applicable in Islamic religious education (Sabilillaq et al., 2024). As watching and observing live or symbolic model performing religious practices consistently and correctly, children are more likely to imitate and internalize those behaviors. Similarly, another study examines Ramadan episode for grade 1 of Upin & Ipin and explains that the series depict worship practices (prayer, fasting, paying zakat). Meanwhile, ghiru mahdah worship includes respecting elders, spreading kindness, helping each other, praying, and being patient that help young viewers to internalize Islamic values and rituals (Rohaeni et al., 2024). Through the figured worlds tool of Gee (2011), the repeated depiction of characters performing rituals and religious practices establishes a “figured world” of Islamic practice in which children come to see these behaviors as normal parts of everyday life.

Repetition and Scaffolding

The recurrent appearance of key Islamic terms, Allah, Quran, Hadith, Salah, “SubhanAllah,” “Alhamdulillah,” “InshaAllah,” “Astaghfirullah,” “Bismillah,” “JazakAllah,” and the greetings “Assalamu Alaikum” and “Wa Alaikum Assalam” reinforces religious vocabulary and in this discourse the repetition of these expressions function as memory-building technique. In different contexts the repetition of behavioural rules like not lying, walking carefully, respecting food, controlling anger, helping others, and using the right hand, saying Bismillah, apologizing to others, strengthens moral internalization and supports linguistic familiarity with Islamic expressions to use appropriately in daily interactions. The scaffolding strategy is also used where Ghulam Rasool and Kaneez Fatima teach complex phenomenon into simpler terms

from confusion to understanding such as the respect of sacred papers, the manners of drinking water, manners of eating, story of Mir'aj, the meaning of steadfastness, finality of Prophethood, and teaching about importance of Islamic Libas for women into small, manageable steps and easy way, guiding the child from partial understanding towards full competence. This approach directly reflects Vygotsky's (1978) sociocultural theory which argues that children learn best when they receive guidance within their Zone of Proximal Development, where learning occurs through supportive assistance from a more knowledgeable figure such as Kaneez Fatima, Ghulam Rasool prominently and their dad rarely. Repetition then reinforces these scaffolded lessons. Bruner (1974) argues the assertion of revisiting core ideas in repeated cycles deepens mastery. Repetition and scaffolding appear as the pedagogical strategies to teach important Islamic concept and values in easy way that reinforces internalizing those religious norms through repeated usage. In essence, the both series exhibit the discourse that combines Gee's small "d" discourse that is language in use in everyday instruction. And with Bandura's theory, these series provide symbolic models that reflect the educational models through which language performs, demonstrates and reinforces religious and moral values.

Conclusion

The discourse of Kaneez Fatima and Ghulam Rasool animated series contribute in the formation of religious identity through moral exemplification, repeated corrective feedback, contextual reinforcement and behavioral modeling. The study findings highlight the use of different pedagogical approaches through expressions such as "should" and "remember"—as well as through moral reinforcement using words like "reward," "help," "forgive," and "apologize." Such approaches identified in series are; direct instruction through commands, reinforcement strategies, audience engagement strategies, modeling through demonstration, repetition and scaffolding. Characters frequently guide children through ritual procedures, model morally acceptable conduct, and address viewers directly using phrases like "Dear children." Such strategies align with Gee's Situated Meaning and Social Languages tools, which show how specific lexical choices shape children's understanding of religious obligations. They also confirm Bandura's proposition that modeling, reinforcement, and observational learning are essential mechanisms through which children acquire new behaviors.

The animated content, therefore, acts as a pedagogical agent, transforming complex Islamic concepts into accessible visual and verbal lessons. Through narrative modelling, these animated

series teach Islamic ethics and social values by serving as informal pedagogical tools. The use of corpus-assisted method revealed the intentional and consistent discourses aimed at guiding young audiences towards Islamic ethical living in the society with modern and liberal beliefs borrowed from other countries' views through media, language and culture. Overall, these series function as powerful tools for shaping children's Islamic views constructed on religiously grounded children's identities in Pakistani context.

References

- Abdullah, M. A. R. (2023). Learning moral values through cartoons for Malaysian preschool-aged children. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 22(6), 370-394.
- Aidulsyah, F. (2023). The rise of urban Salafism in Indonesia: The social-media and pop culture of new Indonesian Islamic youth. *Asian Journal of Social Science*, 51(4), 252-259.
- Al Mushaiqri, M. R. S., & Sulistio, D. (2024). Digital Narratives and Tradition: The Role of NU Kids Animations in Early Islamic Education. *Al-Athfal: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak*, 10(2), 121-133.
- Arnheim, R. (1969). *Visual thinking*. Berkeley: University of California Press
- Bandura, A., & Walters, R. H. (1977). *Social learning theory* (Vol. 1, pp. 141-154). Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice Hall
- Barlex, D., & Carré, C. (1985). *Visual communication in science*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Bliss, J., Ogborn, J., & Whitelock, D. (1989). Secondary pupils' commonsense theories of motion. *International Journal of Science Education*, 11, 261-272.
- Bruner, J. S. (1974). *Toward a theory of instruction*. Harvard university press.
- Dewi, N. M. L. C., & Negara, I. G. A. O. (2021). Meningkatkan semangat belajar siswa melalui video animasi IPA pada pokok bahasan sistem pernapasan kelas V. *Jurnal Edutech Undiksha*, 9(1), 122-130.
- Faqihuddin, A., Firmansyah, M. I., & Muflih, A. (2024). Multisensory Approach in Memorizing the Al-Quran for Early Childhood: Integration of the Tradition of Memorizing the Al-Quran with Digital Technology. *ALISHLAH: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 16(2), 1289-1302.
- Fisher, R. (1990). *Teaching children to think*. Oxford: Blackwell Science

- Gee, J. P. (2011). *How to do discourse analysis*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Gee, J. P. (2011). Discourse vs. discourse. *James Paul Gee: Mary Lou Fulton Presidential Professor of Literacy Studies*. Available from jamespaulgee.com/pdfs/Big D Discourse.pdf.
- Heryanto, A. (2014). *Identity and pleasure: The politics of Indonesian screen culture*. nus Press.
- Ishak, M. S. B. H., & Solihin, S. M. (2012). Islam and media. *Asian Social Science*, 8(7), 263.
- Juliansyahzen, M. I. (2023). Ideologization of hijrah in social media: Digital activism, religious commodification, and conservative domination. *Millah: Journal of Religious Studies*, 155-180.
- Lewis, B. (2014, July). The digital age: A challenge for Christian discipleship. In *Proceedings of the European Conference on social media (July, 10-11 2014, Brighton, UK)* (pp. 277-83).
- Lia, L. K. A., Atikah, C., & Nulhakim, L. (2023). Pengembangan media pembelajaran video animasi berbasis animaker untuk meningkatkan hasil belajar siswa SD. *Jurnal Ilmiah Pendidikan Citra Bakti*, 10(2), 386-400.
- Meuleman, J. (2011). Dakwah, competition for authority, and development. *Bijdragen tot de taal, land-en volkenkunde/Journal of the Humanities and Social Sciences of Southeast Asia*, 167(2-3), 236-269.
- Mushtaq, S., & Fatima, H. (2024). Effects of Cartoon Series on Learning Attitude. *UCP Journal of Mass Communication*, 2(2), 52-64.
- Rohaeni, N., Suryani, D., & Wahyudi, I. (2024). Upin and Ipin Animation Ramadan Episode Contains Islamic Values for Grade 1 Students of Madrasah Ibtidaiyyah Al-Huda I. *Pionir: Jurnal Pendidikan*, 13(2), 94-105.
- Sabilillahq, I., Nursiah, A., & Munir, M. (2024). Analysis of Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory and Its Development in Islamic Religious Education. *Reslaj: Religion Education Social Laa Roiba Journal*, 6, 12.
- Suryana, D., & Hijriani, A. (2022). Pengembangan media video pembelajaran tematik anak usia dini 5-6 tahun berbasis kearifan lokal. *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 6(2), 1077-1094.
- Tafonao, T. (2018). Peranan media pembelajaran dalam meningkatkan minat belajar mahasiswa. *Jurnal komunikasi pendidikan*, 2(2), 103-114.
- Warini, S., Zakir, S., & Murdiana, M. (2024). Development Of Islamic Religious Education Learning Media Based on Animation Videos. *FOKUS Jurnal Kajian Keislaman dan Kemasyarakatan*, 9(2), 123-135.

- Wei, M. (2024). Mediatization of religion and its impact on youth identity formation in contemporary China. *Religions*, 15(3), 268.
- Yahya, Y. K., Fajari, I. A., & Mahmudah, U. (2021, February). Da'wah on Youtube: An effort in Islamic values representation. In *ICIS 2020: Proceedings of the 2nd International Conference on Islamic Studies, ICIS 2020, 27-28 October 2020, Ponorogo, Indonesia* (p. 153). European Alliance for Innovation.
- Yolcu, P., & Çiftçi, H. (2023). Teaching Religious Education Through Cartoons: The Case of Ramazan Tayfa Cartoon Film. *Gümüşhane Üniversitesi İletişim Fakültesi Elektronik Dergisi*, 11(1), 622-
- Yoshida, K. (2008). *Animation and "otherness": The politics of gender, racial, and ethnic identity in the world of Japanese anime* (Doctoral dissertation). University of British Columbia Vancouver.
- Yousaf, M. A., Dar, H. M. U., & ain Shafique, Q. (2022). Cartoons as A Tool of Religious Instruction for School-Going Children: A Case Study of Sheikhpura City. *Wah Academia Journal of Social Sciences*, 1(01), 40-52.
- Zaid, B., Fedtke, J., Shin, D. D., El Kadoussi, A., & Ibahrine, M. (2022). Digital Islam and Muslim millennials: How social media influencers reimagine religious authority and Islamic practices. *Religions*, 13(4), 335.
- Zulfiqar, W., & Ahmed, R. Z. (2025). Moral Symbolism and Social Struggle in Pakistani Animation: An Iconographic Analysis of 3 Bahadur. *AlQamar*, 81-110.